

Between Tradition and Modernity: Patriarchy and Power Dynamics in #ArewaMeToo Discussions on X Platform

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Abstract

Background: Language is crucial to the production of discourses that legitimize sexual violence and rape since language is a symbolic system of power. It is through such power of discourse, that sexual violence and rape victims form linguistic narratives that enable them to share their experiences.

Objective: This research examines the patriarchal, religious, and cultural practices that legitimise sexual violence in Nigeria on the X platform.

Methodology: This study employed a qualitative design using Fairclough's model of Critical Discourse Analysis. Data were purposively gathered and thematically coded. The sampled tweets comprise 100, manually gathered from #ArewaMeToo on X, produced by Nigerians. These tweets were numbered randomly from T1 to T100 based on how the data was gathered. ('T' represents tweets).

Results: Results indicate that strong religious and cultural explanations underpin the prevalence of rape and sexual violence practices in Northern Nigeria. It also provides evidence that patriarchal power structures enhance these practices. This accounts for the prevalence of certain ideologies that accompany such events, such as the ideology of silence and fear, shame, and stigma.

Unique Contribution: This study has revealed how X serves as a platform for users to express opinions on posts made by survivors and victims' experiences of rape and sexual violence.

Conclusion: This study concludes that the conversations on the Nigerian X platform reflect some ideological perspectives and contentions underlying rape and sexual violence as well as reactions showing disapproval for such ideologies.

Recommendation: Further studies may embark on a critical discourse analysis of other hashtags that address rape and sexual violence and a critical discourse analysis of gender inequality using other social media platforms.

Keywords: Patriarchy, power, sexual violence, Nigeria, critical discourse analysis

Introduction

The phrase ‘Arewa, Me Too’ was created to emphasize the severity of domestic and gender-based violence in northern Nigeria. It includes the phrase ‘Arewa,’ a Nigerian name for northern Nigeria, and the worldwide hashtag #MeToo, which refers to a societal movement against sexual abuse. While women in a patriarchal nation like Nigeria experience threats and risks, the dangers of being a woman are amplified in the north, where religion and collectivism are frequently utilised as oppressive instruments. Northern Nigeria is a religiously conservative region with obsolete family laws based on Islamic doctrine, which asserts that men have God-given control over women in marriages, divorces, and custody cases (Jenyo, 2018). Most states in northern Nigeria still adhere to Sharia Law (Islamic religious law), which justifies constraints on the enhancement and preservation of women’s fundamental human rights. This form of culture and Islamic ideology makes it difficult for sexual abuse victims to come out. Fearing stigmatisation, police extortion, and a lack of faith in the court system, some victims and their families opt not to disclose crimes to authorities.

The hashtag #ArewaMeToo was used to bring sexual assault to the attention of Nigerians, particularly in northern Nigeria. Fakhariyya Hashim initially used the hashtag #ArewaMeToo in February 2019 to highlight the narrative of a lady who opted to narrate her story of sexual violence on social media, following the worldwide #MeToo movement’s lead. Hashim’s tweet sparked a firestorm of replies, much to the #MeToo hashtag. Soon after, women and girls throughout Nigeria began sharing their stories of sexual and domestic violence, shattering the taboo. The fact that the event took place in northern Nigeria, with its primarily conservative Muslim population, added to its significance. What brought about #ArewaMeToo was the failure of the government and the failure of the society, and this is coming from an ultra-conservative position.

#ArewaMeToo launched a campaign in Nigeria against rape, domestic violence and other forms of gender-based violence called the ‘North Normal Stand Still Rally’. The movement attracted the attention of numerous legal and media professionals including Kadaria Ahmed, among others. The plan for the standstill rally was in protest of the fact that only 18 people have been convicted of rape in Nigeria. The movement called for the adoption of the *Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act (VAPP)* and members of #ArewaMeToo also demanded capital punishment for rapists. Significantly and luckily, the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Measure (VAPP) went into effect on May 25, 2015, however, it took 14 years for the National Assembly to enact the bill into law. The act also allows courts to give proper compensation to victims of rape and other forms of violence in the country. On X, hashtags such as #StandStillRally, #NorthNormal, and #NoToSGBV also supported the #ArewaMeToo campaign. This campaign gained traction in northern states such as Niger State, Bauchi State, Borno State, Kaduna State, Sokoto State, Yobe

State, and Kano State. The campaign created awareness of the importance of breaking the culture of silence and shame with regard to sexual violence.

Objective of the Study

This research seeks to examine the link between patriarchy, culture, religion, and digital activism within the #ArewaMeToo movement on the X platform. In addition, the research aims to examine how patriarchal norms, culture, and religion are embedded in the ideological representations of sexual violence within #ArewaMeToo discussions on X platform. By analysing the discourse it will investigate how culture, religion, and patriarchal norms are integrated with online discourse.

Gender, Patriarchy, and Power Relations in Northern Nigeria

Patriarchy, according to Igbelina-Igbokwe (2013), is a system of social stratification and differentiation based on sex that offers material benefits to men while enforcing extreme limitations on female duties and tasks, with several taboos to guarantee adherence to established gender roles. Patriarchy, according to this perspective, is a hierarchical structure in which men have power over women, which is manifested in the beliefs, norms, traditions, assumptions, and organisations of the society and preserved via the system of socialisation. Defining the concept further from the perspective of domination over women, the London Feminist Network maintains that patriarchy is the term used to represent the society in which we live today, defined by the present and past unequal power relations between women and men, whereby women are systematically marginalised and victimised. Women's lack of representation in important governmental institutions, decision-making positions, employment, and commerce is particularly prominent. A significant aspect of patriarchy is a male assault on women. As a result, the London Feminist Network considers women's abuse to be an intrinsic aspect of patriarchy.

In Nigeria, patriarchy is linked with authoritarian, dominating masculinity and is defined by social domination, which is mainly exhibited in men (Gesinde, 2020). It is a social, psychological, political, and emotional instrument that shapes women's perceptions of themselves as helpless objects of subjugation, fear, and victims of harsh and unjust treatment (Dogo, 2014). In Nigeria, patriarchy is perpetuated through training males to understand and demonstrate their power, while women are trained to defer to masculine authority. Men also learn to exert dominance through hostility and brutality, which is normal behaviour for them; women, on the other hand, must stay composed and obedient (Idowu, 2013). Thus, patriarchy is a social structure centred on male-dominated, male-identified, and male-cultured institutions. In Nigeria, various examples of women's rights violations have happened over the last decade, including sexual violence, the killing of women, rape, widow abuse and physical attacks. Unfortunately, the media and police are primarily interested in extreme cases of women's rights violations which end in death or lifelong impairment. Female circumcision or genital mutilation, wife battering, marital rape, sexual harassment, verbal and emotional abuse, incest, loss of work as a result of pregnancy, and other significant incidents are not regarded as serious enough to be publicized or treated seriously by the authorities (Ademiluka, 2018). Victims of abuse, particularly sexual violence and rape, seldom disclose their crimes to the police. In a typical patriarchal society such as northern Nigeria, the woman is seen as the property of her husband who has the moral right to beat her as a punishment for insubordination or perceived wrongdoing. When it comes to rape, women see it as a societal

disgrace if their suffering is made public (Okunlola et al., 2020). In addition, regulations in Nigeria that safeguard women from violence are grossly ineffective. For example, marital rape is not often considered an offense in any justice system whether the woman is hurt during coerced sexual contact. The Penal Code of Northern Nigeria explicitly prohibits any action that does not cause serious harm and is committed by a husband to correct his wife; such husband and wife are bound by natural law or tradition that permits such correction and is recognised as lawful. (Jaiyeola & Aladegbola, 2020). This implies that the law, through the Penal Code, tolerates the pervasive issue of sexual violence by encouraging husbands to beat their spouses as long as it does not cause irreparable damage. Furthermore, Mshelia (2021) maintains that in Nigeria, religion is utilised as a weapon to defend a class system and patriarchy, which makes it biased against women. Due to the theocratic nature of administration in northern Nigeria before the arrival of British colonialists, Islam has been established as a culture-a way of life-for the vast majority of people in the region. The Sharia (Islamic law) prioritises paternalistic interpretations of women's suitable responsibilities and the socio-political organisation of society. Sharia law contradicts national secular values, particularly those about women's rights, on which Nigeria is constitutionally founded (Mshelia 2021).

X as a Platform for Social Activism and Civic Engagement

X is a micro-blogging social networking site that permits individuals to communicate by sharing messages online. It is a large networking site that lets users share information with their followers. X has proven to be more productive in social movements as a significant and visible social networking platform. X fosters clarity, confidentiality, safety, and mutual relationships among activists and provides a forum for collective activities. Although some have criticised X's efficacy in protest movements (Bennet & Segerberg, 2011), others have discovered that it is a powerful platform for transmitting information (Hermida et al., 2014). X is a global platform. Thus, information spreads very quickly, enabling activists, for example, to take fast actions that result in rapid mobilisation. X promotes collective action by providing users with a platform to interact, encouraging collective identity establishment, raising public awareness, and coordinating peaceful demonstrations and online movements (Chimuanya et al., 2015). These online movements are usually focused around a single hashtag that represents a certain social problem and conveys the movement's fundamental purpose, for instance, #ArewaMeToo.

Theoretical Framework

Fairclough's dialectical-relational approach considers discourse to be part of the social process. From this perspective, discourse is dialectically related to social relations, power, institutions, beliefs, and cultural values. Fairclough's Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a methodology that studies covert and explicit structural relations of authority, injustice, power, and control as represented in the language. CDA aims to make the opaque components of discourse more visible and transparent. Fairclough (2009) defined discourse as a social practice and developed the concept of 'discursive practice' as a mediating 'third dimension' between linguistic aspects of a text and social practice. Through deconstructing the society, this approach aims to investigate possible social inequalities as represented, produced, and legitimised through discursive practices.

The discursive practice involves the language developed around processes of text production, distribution, and consumption (Fairclough, 2009).

Materials and Methods

The data for this study, which aims to analyse victims' perspectives and opinions on sexual violence and rape through the #ArewaMeToo discourse, employs a qualitative research design. The data was gathered purposively from posts on the X platform on sexual violence and rape experiences produced by Nigerians. The database comprised many tweets; a sample of approximately 500 tweets was retrieved manually from X. Out of 100 tweet samples, 29 were reproduced in this study. These sampled tweets are numbered randomly from T1 to T100 based on how the data was gathered. ('T' represents tweets). The tweets in the sample were collected without regard to gender, age, or location (within Nigeria). The English language and Nigerian pidgin were used as a filter. Thus, only tweets in the English language and Nigerian pidgin were analysed. For this research, X serves as an appropriate case study because the #ArewaMeToo social movement started on X, and it has been proven that X utilisation is becoming increasingly prevalent during events (Statista, 2018). Tweets were studied from February 2018 to June 2022 from the #ArewaMeToo hashtag that was trending in Nigeria's X platform by famous X accounts that publicised the issue, such as @WaasiShaffii, @FakhuusHashim and @BDakolo. The time frame for this study corresponds to the period during which #ArewaMeToo started. This hashtag was selected after careful consideration because it addressed discussions regarding crucial concepts that influence sexual violence and rape among women in Nigeria, directly or indirectly.

Results and Discussions

Ideological Representation that Reflects Patriarchy and Power in #ArewaMeToo

In the north, rape victims are frequently seen to be aiding their abuse through provocative behaviours and inappropriate dressing as seen below in T5 and T20.

T5 If she was modest, she wouldn't be raped.

It is evident that individuals in contemporary northern Nigerian society continue to 'justify rape' and cling to outdated stereotypes about rape and sexual assault. One of such ideologies is blaming the victim. Persons in northern Nigeria still hold onto obsolete patriarchal ideologies about sexual assault victims on X, such as: 'Why didn't she scream', 'She was enjoying it', and 'Why didn't she shout'. Below are some of the misconceptions that dominated the conversations on X regarding patriarchal ideologies on rape in Nigeria. (Original tweets that discuss patriarchal issues were either deleted or the account suspended, hence this study uses reactions from the comments of the initial tweets.)

*T21 people will say ‘Why didn’t she scream!?’ ‘She was enjoying it!!!’
Research shows that 70% of rape victims are paralysed by fear during the act!!!*

The assumption that the victim ‘was enjoying it’ (T21) is another patriarchal ideology of rape in the north. This is due to the presumption that the victim should have ‘screamed’ (T21) ‘kicked or shouted’ (T60) during the incident, probably to attract attention and request assistance. It is believed that because the victim did not ‘shout, scream or kick’ the perpetrator, then the victim must have enjoyed being raped. This explains why comments like ‘she should have kicked him’ (T60) and ‘why didn't she scream or shout’ (T21). Therefore, female silence is a typical reaction to male aggression. It is for this reason that rape is chronically under-reported in northern Nigeria, rape is seldom reported owing to the high social shame, placed on people who have been raped, the fear of being rejected by their families, or being exposed to violence.

Assigning labels to rape is one of the patriarchal ideologies rape is being justified. In a bid to justify rape, individuals assign labels such as ‘consented rape (T38)’ and ‘surprise sex (T77)’ to legitimize rape. This is illustrated in the data below.

T77 One person writes on their Facebook wall that rape is not a crime, it's just surprise sex.

On the Nigerian X platform, it is evident that individuals constantly construct post-hoc justifications or excuses for morally reprehensible actions. The narrative such as questioning why a survivor did not ‘scream’, ‘kick’, or resist reinforces the perception that a woman is responsible for preventing sexual violence which aligns with the broader patriarchal structure of women upholding sexual morality while excusing the actions of men. The assumption that silence equals consent aligns with Bawa and Mohammed (2024) and demonstrates how sexual violence is minimized with the burden of proof on survivors rather than the perpetrators. In addition, this also

strengthens the idea that resistance is a yardstick for being considered a true victim of sexual violence. The perpetrators of sexual violence and rape often use post-assault defences or justifications to place the responsibility on the victim. The labels given to the act of sexual violence or rape (such as consented rape or surprise sex) can have a significant impact on how people view the event and the roles of the people involved. These labels often times are used to rationalize and mitigate the severity of the crime. Furthermore, the narrative that men are naturally driven by sexual urges and it is the place of the woman to regulate male desire by dressing 'modestly' shifts the responsibility away from the perpetrators. This belief is rooted in a patriarchal structure which creates an environment where sexual violence is justified.

The different ways patriarchy is reflected in northern Nigeria legitimize the rape of the victim by the culprits through discrediting aspects of the rape (surprise sex, consented rape), the victim (she was enjoying it), or the perpetrator. According to the data above, X users' reactions to rape and sexual violence incidents reaffirmed the prevailing patriarchal ideologies about rape in northern Nigeria.

Religious Underpinning behind Rape that reflects Patriarchy and Power Relations

The religious underpinning behind rape is the discourse on child marriage. The discourse on underage union in Northern Nigeria by researchers has been tied to the concept that the prevalence of underage union is primarily due to the Islamic doctrine (T10). This claim is reinforced by three explicit references. Firstly, Tade and Udechukwu (2018) referenced that in Islam, the age to be wedded is believed to be influenced by pubescence (T88). Secondly, is the historical account of Aisha's betrothment to the prophet Muhammad at the age of nine and the consummation of their marriage at the age of thirteen (T18). This is often cited by northern Muslims as a rationale for underage union, notwithstanding that in Nigeria, the legal age of consent is 18 years. Below are examples of tweets that religiously underpin patriarchy and power relations.

T10 Until the North learns that marrying these underage girls in the name of religion is wrong.

T88 And this will keep happening since northern men want to marry 12-year-old girls in the name of their faux religious beliefs which oppress women.

T13 To these Northerners (some, mainly the poor and uneducated ones), marriage is a subjugation of a woman to a man (it's not about love). These under-18 girls just endure the psychological effects of the marriage till old age.

T18 A thirteen-year-old can easily be sexually attractive and active. Can't, you remember that the noble prophet married Sayyada Aisha at the age of thirteen?

T58 Only in Nigeria a 54-year-old pervert can marry a 9-year-old baby and produce babies who end up becoming almajiri, it won't be marriage but rape. Ideology from #Islam is cancer.

T46 Paedophilia is disgusting. Taking religion as a tool to defend a rapist is even worse

The aforementioned tweets provide credence to the claim that rape is, in fact, patriarchal in northern Nigeria under the cloak of religion. Particularly in T13, the user claims that although marriage is widespread in the north, the females getting married off also seem to be marginalised in their marriages, and their ethnicity and religion support this marginalisation. T30 explains that Muslims are permitted to marry little girls and are to consummate the marriage when the girl reaches puberty. T29 furthers this claim by justifying that the female reaches adulthood before her first menstruation, which is why they are married off at a young age, because they are perceived as adults. The marriage is consummated when the girl reaches puberty which is potentially rape. T64 expresses displeasure with an imperative sentence, imploring Muslims to ‘stop using religion to justify paedophilia’ and to acknowledge that these are girls, not brides. A similar claim is made by T58, who claims that such a union ‘will not be marriage but rape’ and that this ‘ideology from #Islam is a cancer’ in society. T46 argues in favour of this viewpoint that while ‘paedophilia is disgusting’, using ‘religion as a shield for rapists is even worse’.

The patriarchal ideology embedded in these discussions constructs female subjugation as divinely sanctioned, making resistance difficult. This aligns with Afolabi and Shaffi's (2024) argument that rape, child marriage, and gender inequality are not only cultural problems but it is reinforced through religious framings. These religious interpretations are then used to justify and sustain sexual violence through patriarchal dominance. These discussions reveal insights into how patriarchal structures are cloaked under religious doctrine and how patriarchal institutions deflect accountability, silence survivors, and normalise harmful practices.

Patriarchy Reflected through the Ideology of Silence in Arewa: Breaking the Silence

Victims of rape dread the repercussions of speaking up about what transpired to them and fear being isolated because they end up with a form of double peril. Due to this, most victims would rather not speak up and intensify their misery than risk doing so and losing all sources of assistance. T32 below illustrates patriarchy rooted in the ideology of silence.

T7 It is happening. It has started! Time to speak your truth. Step up! Stand for! Accept Nothing Less. It is time to stop being silent!

In northern Nigeria, the ideology of silence is pervasive. In T32, the user expresses solidarity with other users by employing the third-person plural ‘we’ to inspire other users to stand against the culture of silence. Employing an exclamatory phrase, the user asserts that they ‘will not inherit the silence of our mothers’. In this context, Mother alludes to the past generation who have remained silent, rather than speaking up. In T7 the user incentivises other users to ‘speak their truth’ and ‘stop being silent’ therefore breaking away from the silent tradition.

T19 Don't be ashamed of your story, it will inspire others.

T51 You are strong and you have inspired so many of us to speak up and speak our truth even if the world will judge us! I understand and felt every single moment you spoke about and I share in your pain.

T72 People who take sides and shift blame when an incident of rape or sexual assault occurs are as guilty as the perpetrator. Dear survivor, SPEAK YOUR TRUTH.

In contemporary times, rape victims have begun to come out to break the culture of silence and share their experiences. In T19, the user urges victims of rape not to be ‘ashamed of their story or

experience adding that it will rather inspire others to share theirs. In T51, the user encourages others by responding to how another user's experience has motivated other victims to 'speak up and speak their truth' despite the criticism, victimization, and backlash they will receive. In T72 and T68 the users encourage victims to 'speak their truth and 'call out the rapist'.

The discussion reveals that silence in Northern Nigeria is deeply embedded in cultural and patriarchal structures which supports Malefakis's (2022) argument that victims and survivors of sexual violence are expected to live through the trauma rather than speak out. The discussions illustrate how silence is not an individual choice but a societal expectation enforced through cultural norms, gender roles, and fear of victimisation. The #ArewaMeToo movement challenges this silence through digital activism to empower survivors to speak up and seek justice.

Patriarchy and Power Relation Reflected in the Ideology of Fear, Shame and Stigma

Patriarchal attitudes and behaviours that are dominant in northern society make it impossible for women who have been raped to receive justice (T2), and as a result, rape victims suffer in silence owing to the shame and humiliation associated with confessing to being raped in public. Below are examples of tweets that illustrate patriarchy reflected in the ideology of fear, shame, and stigma.

T2 This is the country and you think victims should find it easy to talk about their rape? Y'all don't even know the trauma. The shock. The denial. The shame. The stigma. The insanity that follows with rape

In T2, the user asserts that in Nigeria, it is challenging for rape victims to share their experiences because of the 'trauma, the shock, the denial, the shame and the stigma' that comes with publicizing the incident. Similarly, T93, adds that rape is not limited to sex, it entails the stigma and shame that comes with it. In a traditional northern setting, victims of rape would rather stay in silence than speak up because of the social isolation which is accompanied by shame and stigmatization. The social stigma or guilt that society ascribes to the victim is a contributing factor to the victim's silence.

T44 Pathetic! I heard a woman whose 3-year-old was sexually abused by her school teacher, silenced the story because she didn't want the daughter to be stigmatized going forward.

Many families in the north would prefer to cover up the crime, even if it means going against the victim's wishes, since they are scared of tarnishing the family's reputation. As a result, women in northern Nigeria choose to remain hidden rather than seek justice. At times, a response to sexual violence by the family backfires on the victim. Some families blame the women while sparing the perpetrator's punishment and instead focus on regaining lost family reputation, which fosters an atmosphere where rape may happen without consequence. Though families frequently strive to protect their daughters from rape, there is rarely any social effort to regulate or persuade young males that forceful sex is bad.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Although prior studies investigate rape and sexual violence from different perspectives such as health, psychology, media, etc. this study has been able to examine rape and sexual violence from a linguistic perspective, in that the study examined the social and cultural practices that legitimize sexual violence and gender inequality in Nigeria, as well as analyse the discursive structures of conversations about sexual violence on X. In addition, this study has illustrated that conversations on the Nigerian X platform reflect some ideological perspectives and contentions underlying rape and sexual violence as well as complaints and disapproval for such ideologies.

Based on the data from the X platform, the findings of this study indicate that strong religious and cultural explanations underpin the prevalence of rape and sexual violence practices in Northern Nigeria, it also provides evidence that these practices are enhanced by patriarchal power structures and the male exercise of control over the women's life. Power is derived from religious and cultural institutions that permit such practices; hence the practice of women's oppression is enforced via cultural and religious beliefs and practices. The study established a clear link between culture, religious beliefs, and the prevalence of rape and sexual violence in northern Nigeria. It was discovered that the fusion of an individual's deeply embedded cultural beliefs with Islamic principles is the most significant factor fostering rape and sexual violence in the region. It was also revealed that rape and sexual violence are still pervasive in northern Nigeria and are serious social issues in the region.

This research does not only contribute to the understanding of rape and sexual violence from a linguistic perspective but examines how survivors and victims of rape and sexual violence utilize X to express their opinions as well as share experiences. The use of #ArewaMeToo created a social movement encouraging victims of rape and sexual violence to share their experiences. This

demonstrates that X has the potential to spread messages concerning issues affecting marginalized persons, thereby creating a safe space for victims.

This study also contributes to the global feminist discourse on #MeToo, particularly in Nigeria by examining how #ArewaMeToo discussions on the X platform provide evidence that religious, cultural, and social institutions reinforce patriarchal power structures in northern Nigeria. In addition, this study adds to the literature on sexual violence and rape, particularly #MeToo in Nigeria. However further studies may embark on a critical discourse analysis of other hashtags that address rape and sexual violence and a critical discourse analysis of gender inequality using other social media platforms. Also, the theoretical framework presented in this study may be adopted by other researchers to carry out an analysis addressing rape and sexual violence discourses or gender inequality.

Limitation of the Study

The study did not consider the age, gender, or socioeconomic status of the tweet authors, which made it challenging to determine how various demographics interacted with the #ArewaMeToo discourse. Also, tweets were concise, vague, and sometimes without context, making it difficult to interpret the intended meaning completely. In addition, the analysis was based on only 100 tweets, which may not adequately represent the scope of discourse within the #ArewaMeToo movement. A larger dataset might provide a more detailed examination.

Disclosure Statement

The authors have no conflict of interest.

Author's Contribution

LC prepared the initial manuscript, designed the research method, contributed to the analysis and conclusion, and supervised the research.

UU developed the research idea, collected the data for the study, and contributed to the analysis and the conclusion.

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